

Microfinance and Financial Inclusion in India: A Special Focus on Uttarakhand.

Neha Barodia¹ & Anumita Agarwal²

ABSTRACT

Since poverty has continuously been a problem in India and its alleviation remains a prime priority for the government. Financial inclusion has come as a prominent weapon to counter poverty by providing equal access to financial services to weaker sections of society. Despite financial inclusion, the phenomenon of financial exclusion is not letting economic progress take place since poor people have been deprived of participation in the formal financial sector. Here, microfinance has emerged as a revolutionary instrument in filling this gap. Through the extension of small-scale financial services like microloans, savings, and insurance, microfinance institutions enable economically poor people, especially in rural communities, to pursue productive activities, improve their livelihoods, and become financially secure. Microfinance has been a key factor in bringing previously excluded segments of Indian society into the banking system, thus encouraging self-employment and entrepreneurship in India. Being a cost-efficient and sustainable measure, microfinance reinforces efforts towards financial inclusion and economic growth. This paper discusses the role of microfinance in improving financial inclusion in India and examines the comparison expansion of Uttarakhand with the central region and its ability to mitigate financial exclusion, thus ensuring sustainable economic growth and social development.

Keywords: *Micro-finance, financial Inclusion, SHGs.*

Introduction

Financial inclusion has emerged as a critical policy priority for India over the past two decades, with the objective of integrating the underserved and excluded segments of the population into the formal financial system. Defined broadly as the delivery of affordable and appropriate financial services to all individuals, especially the economically weaker sections and low-income groups, financial inclusion is now widely recognized as a cornerstone for inclusive and sustainable development.

As a financial instrument that offers those in need small loans, savings accounts, and insurance, microfinance has become well-known as a successful way to accomplish the more general objectives

-
1. Research Scholar, Department of Economics, P.N.G. Govt. Post Graduate College, Ramnagar, Kumaun University, Nainital (Uttarakhand) E-mail: nehabarodia1215@gmail.com
 2. Professor, Department of Economics, P.N.G. Govt. Post Graduate College, Ramnagar, Kumaun University, Nainital (Uttarakhand)

of financial inclusion. By providing access to capital that promotes entrepreneurship, consumption smoothing, and resilience against economic shocks, microfinance aims to empower economically vulnerable groups, especially women. In India, MFIs have been crucial in providing small loans, particularly to underprivileged groups without collateral. They are making a significant contribution to the nation's financial inclusion movement. There are many different contributors in the microfinance industry, having their own legal structure. Banks, SFBs, NBFCs, NBFC-MFIs, and non-profit MFIs are all included.

Microfinance in India has developed through a number of institutional models, most notably the Joint Liability Group (JLG) model and the Self-Help Group (SHG)–Bank Linkage Program. In addition to democratizing financial access, these models have promoted collective empowerment, mutual accountability, and group cohesion.

The Reserve Bank of India's National Strategy for Financial Inclusion (2019–2024) emphasizes how crucial formal financial services are for raising economic participation, fostering entrepreneurship, and improving livelihoods. In this regard, microfinance institutions (MFIs), such as community-based organizations, cooperative banks, Small Finance Banks (SFBs), and Non-Banking Financial Companies (NBFCs), have become significant players in providing the underprivileged with specialized financial services and products.

There are still regional differences in the reach and efficacy of microfinance, despite notable advancements at the federal level. High penetration levels have been observed in southern and eastern states such as Tamil Nadu, Karnataka, and Bihar, while hilly and isolated areas like Uttarakhand are still relatively underbanked. Because of Uttarakhand's distinct topography and infrastructure, which includes mountainous terrain, dispersed rural communities, and poor physical connectivity, microfinance services have not been able to grow smoothly. However, these very limitations emphasize how crucial it is to create inclusive, region-specific financial strategies that can adapt to local realities.

Objectives

1. To analyse the role of micro finance in achieving financial inclusion.
2. To examine the comparison expansion of Uttarakhand with central region as well as all India level.

Literature Review

(Rangarajan, 2008), highlighted six pillars for improving inclusion, some of which have a direct connection to microfinance. These include using business correspondents and facilitators, strengthening the SHG-Bank Linkage program, and streamlining loan procedures. These factors have influenced the design of India's microfinance ecosystem, which seeks to strike a balance between social impact and financial sustainability. It offers a comprehensive analysis of financial exclusion in India, emphasizing the difficulties disadvantaged populations encounter when trying to obtain official financial services. The report examines global models and makes a number of important suggestions to improve financial inclusion. These include putting in place a National Rural Financial Inclusion Plan, using business correspondents and facilitators, bolstering the SHG-

Bank linkage program, addressing microfinance issues and promoting microinsurance, and enhancing financial education and literacy.

(Chakaraborty, 2013), RBI policy addressed the necessity of context-specific and region-specific financial inclusion initiatives. He urged a variety of strategies, highlighting the difficulties in rural and hilly regions in particular. Despite being insightful at the policy level, the discussion lacked empirical validation and comparative data analysis.

(Maity, 2023), investigated how SHGs contribute to social exclusion and financial inclusion. The study focuses on the three districts of Nagaon, Morigaon, and Hojai in Central Assam. The effect evaluation is conducted using the PSM technique, and the empirical results show that the program significantly improves the financial and social inclusion status of the treated group members relative to the control group members. One well-known model for financially assisting vulnerable groups is the SHG-led microfinance program. In India, the vast majority of participants are housewives. Their involvement enables them to have insurance, work, bank accounts, and ATMs.

(Revankar, 2023), With a focus on both the economic and psychological aspects, this study examines the complex role that microfinance plays in empowering small business owners. Through a primary survey conducted in Belagavi, Karnataka, it identifies the main purposes of microfinance, including enterprise development, financial support, and repayment mechanisms, and investigates their effects. According to the study, the relationship between microfinance services and entrepreneurial empowerment is significantly mediated by financial inclusion. The mediating effect of financial inclusion, though acknowledged, is yet to be explored in a comprehensive framework that integrates both economic and psychological dimensions of empowerment. This study concluded that a thorough approach to microfinance can boost small business owners' confidence and ability.

(Tyagi, 2024), In India, microfinance has made a substantial contribution to socioeconomic development, financial inclusion, and poverty reduction, particularly for underserved communities. Numerous studies demonstrate how well microfinance models such as Joint Liability Groups (JLGs), Microfinance Institutions (MFIs), and Self-Help Groups (SHGs) empower women, increase economic opportunities, and raise living standards. To optimize the sector's impact, however, problems like excessive debt, high interest rates, and regulatory concerns must be addressed through continued innovation and better frameworks. Additionally, the study pinpoints a few critical elements that impact microfinance's efficacy. The impact of microfinance projects can be increased by integrating financial literacy programs, as education has emerged as a critical determinant of success. Furthermore, microfinance results vary by location, indicating that while developing and executing microfinance programs, greater consideration should be given to local circumstances, infrastructure, and the economic climate.

Research Methodology

The Present study was based on secondary data on MICROFINANCE IN INDIA. The major source of data was NABARD Report-2019, 2020,2021,2022,2023,2024..The data included Microfinance especially SHGs trends from 2019-2024 . Different websites , government reports have been referred.

Discussion and Analysis

Role and Importance of Micro- Finance in achieving Financial Inclusion

Particularly for low-income people who frequently face exclusion because of inadequate collateral, erratic income, or a lack of a verified credit history, microfinance is crucial in bridging the gap left by traditional financial institutions. These markets are usually viewed as high-risk and low-yield by traditional banking methods, which results in credit rationing and widespread financial exclusion. Microfinance, on the other hand, uses cutting-edge tactics like social collateral, joint liability, and group lending to successfully reach these marginalized communities. Microfinance institutions (MFIs) have been successful in bringing the unbanked population closer to the formal financial system by offering microinsurance, savings accounts, small, collateral-free loans, and financial education programs. The Reserve Bank of India (RBI) and the Indian government have recognized microfinance as an essential instrument for improving financial inclusion, especially in rural and neglected region.

The provision of a range of financial services, such as loans, savings accounts, insurance, payment systems, and remittance options, to low-income individuals and microbusinesses without access to traditional banking is generally referred to as microfinance. Its ability to reach populations that traditional financial institutions frequently ignore emphasizes its importance in promoting financial development. Microfinance has become one of the most popular strategies for advancing financial inclusion globally, as noted by Pauli (2019). This aligns with the overarching goal of developing sustainable economic structures that serve and involve all socioeconomic groups. In order to create a robust financial system that would promote equitable economic growth, the Indian government took the initiative to nationalize commercial banks. However, infrastructure and socioeconomic constraints make it more difficult to improve financial inclusion in rural areas compared to urban ones (Lopez & Winkler, 2018). As a result, the RBI and the Indian government have set 100% financial inclusion as a national objective, with a particular emphasis on underprivileged and marginalized groups. Globally, microfinance has taken many institutional forms, including the Grameen model and individual banking, and it has continuously shown advantages for both lenders and borrowers. By giving people access to official financial services, microfinance strengthens its position as a source of economic empowerment and fosters social integration for marginalized people.

Microfinance Services

1. Microcredit
2. Micro saving
3. Microinsurance
4. Micro Loans
5. Money Transfer

Microfinance Service Providers

1. **Formal institutions:** Rural Banks, Co-operative Banks, Grameen Model Banks
2. **Semiformal Institutions:** Non-Government Institutions
3. **Informal Institutions:** Money lenders, Shopkeepers.

- 1987: NABARD marked the beginning of microfinance in India by sanctioning an Action Research Project to MYRADA.
- 1992: It was a crucial turning point with NABARD initiating a pilot project to connect 500 SHGs to banks by 1994 and the RBI/NABARD introducing core innovations like accepting informal groups as bank customers, initiating collateral-free lending, and lending to groups without specific activity/purpose projects.
- 1996: RBI's announcement of the SHG-BLP as a Priority Sector Lending (PSL) activity and recommending 3 models of SHG-BLP further institutionalized and popularized the program, and 4,750 SHGs were credit-linked with bank credit.
- 1998: NABARD was required by the Union Budget to credit-link 2 lakh SHGs in 5 years, thereby greatly increasing the program's ambitions.
- 1999: The Government of India (GoI) showed its commitment by making special budgetary allocations for facilitating SHGs and launched the Swarna Jayanti Gram Swarajgar Yojana (SGSY).
- 2005: NABARD reached the milestone of promoting 1 million SHGs, 3 years ahead of target, and the UN declared 2005 as the 'International Year of Micro Credit', underlining the global significance of microfinance.
- 2008: NABARD floated the Financial Inclusion Fund (FIF) & Financial Inclusion Technology Fund (FITF) with a corpus size of ₹ 500 crore, established the Centre for Microfinance Research (CMR) at BIRD, Lucknow, and created a microfinance subsidiary, NABFINS.

According to NABARD, in 36 States and Union Territories, microfinance activities are dispersed among 641 districts. With 636 districts, banks are the most prevalent, followed by SFBs (616 districts) and NBFC-MFIs (613 districts). Nonprofit MFIs operate in 384 districts, whereas NBFCs operate in 538 districts. While the microfinance penetration rate is higher in southern states like Tamil Nadu, Karnataka, and Kerala and eastern states like West Bengal, Odisha, Bihar, etc., it is primarily below 10% in regions like J&K, coastal Maharashtra, Western Uttar Pradesh, Uttarakhand, etc.

Micro lenders are active in 113 of the 124 aspirational districts, where microfinance penetration ranges from 25% to 50%.

The 2019 KPMG report states that the Indian microfinance industry served over 9 crore customers and had a Gross Loan Portfolio (GLP) of ₹ 1.87 lakh crore. With more than 80% of the credit concentrated in just ten states such as Bihar, Odisha, Maharashtra, Uttar Pradesh, West Bengal, Tamil Nadu, Madhya Pradesh, Rajasthan, Chhattisgarh and Gujrat. This growth has been extremely concentrated. The fact that states like Uttarakhand did not rank highly in the national microfinance portfolio indicates that more focused policy interventions and regionally specific models are required to increase financial inclusion in underserved areas.

Models for achieving Financial inclusion through MFIs:

1. **SHGs:** Since independence, the SHG-Bank Linkage Program has been the most effective means of providing sustainable financial services to the underprivileged. As a result of the program’s quick expansion, as of March 31, 2007, 29.25 lakh SHGs had been sponsored.
2. **JLGs:** Linking SHGs with banks has become a successful way to provide credit to low-income customers. However, some groups of people in poverty, like tenant farmers, sharecroppers, and oral lessees, have substantially higher borrowing needs but lack the collateral needed to meet the banking system’s conventional financing methods. Joint Liability Groups (JLGs), an improvement on the SHG concept, may be a useful tool for serving these clients. During 2004–05, NABARD launched a project for the creation and connection of JLGs in eight states throughout the nation using 13 RRBs.

PROGRESS OF SAVINGS LINKAGE OF SHGS WITH BANKS (2019 to 2024)

Table 1: Savings of SHGs with Banks:

Year	No. of SHGS			Savings		
	Uttarakhand	Central Region	India	Uttarakhand	Central region	India
2019-20	73973	1135083	10243323	10689.53	171217.00	2615204.89
2020-21	65659	1345575	11223400	12982.89	211869.77	3747761.37
2021-22	81588	1355564	11893053	27539.37	325695.62	4724048
2022-23	93,747	18,32,040	134,03,083	24106.64	458675	5889267.56
2023-24	107988	2031019	14421904	48473.72	623236.08	6508915.27

Source: NABARD Report

Table 2: Loan Disbursal

Year	No. of SHGs			Loan Disbursal		
	Uttarakhand	Central Region	India	Uttarakhand	Central Region	India
2019-20	6346	111074	3146002	4183.58	104249.49	7765934.84
2020-21	8536	128617	2887394.5	7559.35	105428.11	5807067.81
2021-22	9523	184322	3398267	9423.73	216983.17	9972922.5
2022-23	14493	278359	4295521	17932.78	463672.7	14520023.33
2023-24	21729	397413	5482152	28371.91	774839.17	20928587.07

Source: NABARD Report

Table 3: Outstanding Bank Loan against SHGS

Year	No. of SHGS			Outstanding Bank Loan against SHGS		
	Uttarakhand	Central Region	India	Uttarakhand	Central region	India
2019-20	16354	354466	5677071	8881	225097	10807507
2020-21	17850	368271	5780244	9782.48	252282.02	10328970.83
2021-22	21552	407004	6739957	13424	325178	15105130
2022-23	28595	495999	6957051	19504	512131	18807880
2023-24	36805	675625	7741784	28182.02	909735.85	25966372.61

Source: NABARD Report

Reflecting a strong microfinance expansion, the SHG-BLP in India showed notable growth from 2019-20 to 2023-24. Nationally, the number of SHGs rose from 10,243,323 to 14,421,904, with matching savings increase from ₹ 2,615,204.89 lakh to ₹ 6,508,915.27 lakh. While outstanding loans grew from ₹ 10,807,507 lakh to ₹ 25,966,372.61 lakh, loan disbursement also experienced a significant increase from ₹ 7,765,934.84 lakh to ₹ 20,928,587.07 lakh. The Central Region, where SHG numbers climbed from 1,135,083 to 2,031,019, and Uttarakhand, where savings grew from ₹ 10,689.53 lakh to ₹ 48,473.72 lakh, reflect this national trend, suggesting a general deepening of financial inclusion and credit access.

Relative Position of Micro finance in Uttarakhand as on March, 31,2024. (in Lakhs)

Particulars	Savings			Loan Disbursement			Outstanding Bank Loan against SHGS		
	No. of SHGs	Savings	Per SHG	No. of SHGs	Loan Disbursement	Per SHGs	No. of SHGs	Outstanding Bank Loan against SHGS	Per SHGs
Uttarakhand	107988	48473	44,887	21729	28372	130572	36805	28182	76,571
Central region	20,31,019	6,23,236	30,685	3,97,413	7,74,839	194,970	6,75,625	9,09,736	134,651
India	1,44,21,904	65,08,915	45,132	54,82,152	2,09,28,587	381,758	77,41,784	2,59,66,373	33,540
Share of Uttarakhand (at Central level)	5.32%	7.8%		5.47%	3.7%		5.45%	3.1%	
Share of Uttarakhand (at India level)	0.75%	0.74%		0.4%	0.14%		0.48%	0.11%	

Key Observations

1. Scale Difference: The absolute numbers between Uttarakhand, the Central Region, and India show notable difference. Given that Uttarakhand is a smaller component of the Central Region and the Central Region is a part of the whole nation, this is only natural.
2. According to SHG Study: Valuable viewpoint provided by the “Per SHG” numbers is the average financial involvement of single SHGs in every region.

Uttarakhand’s Input: Though smaller, Uttarakhand’s share is still significant. It lets us evaluate the state’s development in the area and the country. For example, Uttarakhand’s Central level savings share is 7.8%, while its India level share is 0.74%.

Conclusion

In India, microfinance has emerged as a vital tool for promoting financial inclusion by successfully bringing underprivileged and marginalized groups into the established financial system. Microfinance empowers economically vulnerable groups by providing basic financial services like insurance, savings accounts, and microloans to people and communities that are typically shut out of mainstream banking. Facilitating self-employment, encouraging entrepreneurship, and fostering resilience against financial vulnerabilities are the means by which this empowerment is accomplished.

In the end, growing and bolstering microfinance programs is essential to promoting equitable and sustainable economic growth and a more just allocation of financial resources and opportunities across the country.

References

1. Chakarabarty, K. C. (2013). RBI Report. *RBI bulletin*.
2. Pauli, M. (2019). The market for 33 percent interest loans: Financial inclusion and microfinance in India. *India Review*, 18(1), 88–111. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14736489.2019.1576988>
3. Fuloria, D. K., & Mishra, S. (2022). A Study of Financial Inclusions in Uttarakhand with Reference to Central Government Schemes (PradhanMantri Jan Dhan Yojana in Dehradun District). *International Journal of Advanced Multidisciplinary Research*, 32-39.
4. Maity, S. (2023). Self-help groups, microfinance, financial inclusion, and social exclusion: Insight from Assam. *Heliyon*, 9(6), e16477. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e16477>
5. Rangarajan, D. C. (2008). *The Committee on Financial Inclusion*. Mumbai.
7. Revankar, P. U. (2023). Role of Micro Finance in Empowerment of Small-Scale Enterprise. *8th International Conference on "Economic Growth and Sustainable Development: Emerging Trends"*, 1-12.
8. Tyagi, R. (2024). Role and Impact of Micro Finance in India. *Journal of Chemical Health Risks*, 516-537.
9. NABARD Report- 2019-2024, MICROFINANCE IN INDIA. (n.d.). www.nabard.org
10. Microfinance – contributions to financial inclusion; opportunity and challenges ahead-KPMG